

USER INTERACTION (UI) SYSTEM FOR PHISHING DETECTION AND VOICE NOTIFICATION

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: 30th Sept., 2025 Accepted: 28th Oct., 2025 Published: 25th Nov., 2025</p> <p>KEYWORDS: URL, Detection, Notification, Phishing, User Interaction</p> <p>DOI:</p> <p>© Copyright 2025 Daniel & Success Distributed under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>How to cite this article: Daniel, U., & Success, (2025). User Interaction (UI) System for Phishing Detection and Voice Notification. International Journal of Research and Reviews in Social and Applied Sciences, 2(1), 389-412. DOI:</p>	<p><i>Phishing attacks pose a challenge to web user's world all over. These attacks from phishing URLs are many and very disturbing to internet users globally. The curiosity by well-meaning security professionals has led to further research, and thus propels the development of newer systems to solve this lingering challenge. The updated detection and notification systems which are User Interface (UI) friendly are been developed in other to curb the gaps of users experiencing phishing attacks via the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) approach. This study demonstrates the use of a user interaction system for phishing URL detection and voice notification. A temporal tokenizer was also generated and used for URL text processing which scanned, recognized characters, symbols and redundant tokens. This made it easier to separate specific features from the URL address and return as a list while also identifying directories, keyword arguments, and extensions. VB.NET was used to at the front end while MYSQL database at the backend to accomplish system goals. The proposed system was tested and delivered satisfactory result demonstrating recommendable efficiency.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

Phishing is an illegal activity that uses fraudulent behavior and technical deception to gain unauthorized access to client-confidential data from users or learning models. Phishing comprises spam mails disguised as genuine with a subject matter or message meant to trick the victims into disclosing sensitive information. In deceptive phishing, email alerts from credit card companies, security departments, banks, suppliers, online payment processors, or IT managers are utilized to

take advantage of the uninformed open. The notification requests that the person receiving it, urgently enters or updates their personal data (Meenu 2018). The necessity for data privacy, protection, and prevention against phishing attempts cannot be overstated. Over the years, technological innovation has led to a significant increase in data through social networks (Jain et al., 2020), IoT gadgets, and online transactions. Phishing is one of the oldest techniques still in use today, despite the fact that cybercriminals are constantly coming up with novel methods to gain entry to networks, applications and data without authorization. Learning algorithms are susceptible to these phishing attacks, and hackers employ them to trick them in order to compromise ML detection power (Kumar et al., 2020). Phishing is a type of cybercrime that is expanding rapidly, and when people respond to messages or submit sensitive information to hackers, their data is put at risk (Iwendi et al., 2020).

Phishing

Phishing is a concept, comparable to fishing in which someone will send out hook in hopes that a user will catch it (Subasi and Kremic 2020). The phisher in this case, tricks users of the web into surfing the web so that they can steal sensitive user data. Phishing is the practice of an invader convincing a user, to divulge sensitive information while the scammer impersonates a reliable online platform in an effort to fool or deceive the user. The attacker would have access to all user information, making it easier for the targets to fall for the phisher's trap because they won't be able to tell the difference between legitimate and phishing sites (Shah et al., 2020). Scams such as phishing keep happening with a greater probability of succeeding than other types of attacks due to users' lack of information and awareness. Phishing attacks prey on people's vulnerabilities. It is getting harder to stop phishing attempts, but it is also crucial to develop new strategies for improving phishing detection methods.

Phishing Attacks

Attackers take a number of measures to gather user information. This may entail taking the subsequent actions: planning, compose text message (emails), attack, gather data and fraud (Shie 2020). The fraudster begins to prepare for an attack. The attacker chooses to create a genuine platform that must be replicated and chooses the unfortunate individuals whose data must be obtained. The attack setup platforms must appear to be real at the planning stage in order to entice victims into supplying sensitive information (Maurya and Jain 2020). The attacker or scammer will send text messages to them in the third stage in order to collect information when the target has been duped by the phisher. The intruder carries out a digital crime like credit card fraud, theft, etc. with the victim's information.

Lifecycle of Phishing Attacks and Cyber Kill Chain

A framework called the "cyber kill chain" was created to describe the many stages of a cyber-attack (Pastor-Galindo et al., 2020). A kill chain includes every stage of an attack, from first access through execution. Among the well-known models created by Lockheed Martin, the Cyber Kill

Chain model, which is still in use today by numerous businesses, demonstrates the model's wide spread adoption across a variety of industries that may or may not be connected to cyber security (Baig et al., 2021). As a result, it has demonstrated the stages of a perpetrator, a concept you can use as a model to begin securing your company in accordance with each stage of the cyber kill chain model (AL-Otaibi et al., 2020). The procedures that go into a cyber-attack as well as the steps that adversaries take to accomplish their objective are covered by the created “cyber kill chain”. This framework can also be used to follow a phishing attempt, which can be broken down into the following steps:

Theoretical Framework

(a). **Deceptive phishing:** The most frequent type of phishing attack is deceptive phishing, which impersonates an actual platform or webpage and sends text messages (or emails) to the user that look to be authentic (Javed et al., 2020). The malicious links in these text messages (or emails) would instruct the recipient to click on the uniform resource locator URL. The phishing website that the attackers have set up will gather all of the user’s login credentials and other sensitive information and send it to the attacker. For instance, the lower case "a" in the email address usercreditcard@amazon.com might be eliminated. Consequently, usercreditcard@mazon.com is used to deceive the user and obtain sensitive information.

(b). **Spear phishing:** The spear phishing attack is comparable to the deceptive phishing kind that only targets one user. The scammers aim to trick someone into giving them private information. A tailored message or email is delivered to the user with the intention of misleading them. The email is personalized to include most of the user's details, such as user name, workplace, designation, and so on (Jain et al., 2020). The most frequently used platform for spear phishing is the social media site like LinkedIn where it is simple for them to find out a user's occupation.

(c). **Whale phishing:** The whaling attack type happens when phishers seek people in positions of power, such as the CEO. Prior to the attack, the perpetrator would spend a great amount of time analyzing the target. The attacker sends an email message to target in order to manipulate them into providing confidential information. Whaling is considered as a very dangerous attack since the people in executive bands have access to the organization’s most confidential information. The intruder sends these individuals an email message to trick the recipient into divulging private information (Kumar 2020). Whaling is regarded as a very hazardous attack because executive bands have the ability to access the most sensitive information about the company.

(d). **Pharming:** Pharming is a subset of phishing that does not require a specific person to be the target. Without needing to be specifically targeted, the attacker can harm a huge number of users. There are two techniques to carryout pharming attack: (a). It entails emailing the target codes that change every local host file on the system. The host files would change the URLs into number strings that the system would utilize to access websites. Even though the target user enters a legitimate URL, this may link them to a malicious website. (b). Another pharming attack technique is called DNS cache poisoning, which modifies the website's domain name system tables but leaves

the local host files unharmed. This causes a target to be unknowingly diverted to inappropriate web pages. The user would think they are visiting a reliable website, but due to poisoning of the DNS, they would actually be visiting a hostile domain (Mittal et al., 2020).

Phishing Attack Detection Techniques

The use of classification techniques like Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Trees as a method to reduce phishing attacks has been discussed in a number of relevant studies. (Alkhalil et al. 2021) conducted study on the phishing attack's lifecycle. His report examines the attack's stages' anatomy, the traits of phishing victims, risks, weaknesses, and cutting-edge phishing tactics. The author supports the significance of raising anti-phishing awareness and developing a better system.

Methodology

VB.NET (Visual Basic.Net) is the adopted program used to develop the application. It was used because it is a multiple-paradigm object oriented programming language. It encompasses encapsulation, inheritance and polymorphism and fondly used by programmers because of its vast libraries and functionalities, which allows developers build a wide range of applications, including desktop applications and also web application as applied in this paper.

Figure 3.1: Activity Diagram of the System

Activity Diagram depicts the flow of activities. A running non-atomic processing within a state machine is referred to as an activity. An activity results in an action, a change in state, or the return of a value. Activity Diagrams frequently include: activity states, action states, and transitions. It

may also have nodes and constraints. Action stages and activity states: An action state is an executable atomic computation that cannot be disassembled. In the Activity diagram below, the process is started, after which the datasets are being loaded and immediately after that, the App scans for URL. If URL isn't present, the process returns to inception for re scanning but if present, it proceeds further to check if URL is legitimate and if yes, the activity flows but if no, it proceeds to flag up a voice alert to notify user of phishing attack detection after which user can exit program.

Figure 3.2: Sequence Diagram of the User Interaction

Sequence Diagram showing the step by step sequence of the proposed model. The models sequence diagram which is known as **User Interaction** for the GUI shows how the user interacts with the Web user interface. From the diagram, the user undergoes registration which is saved directly to the database, after which user logs in upon matching login features and then user gets

validated and proceeds to input URL through the web UI. Going further, the URL is being submitted for prediction and predicted results are fed back to user to check if legitimate, or if phishing is also being detected. Finally, user is being notified as voice engine aids to flag up voice alert to user for prompt notification and classification from model, to be either a malicious or trusted URL.

Table 3.1: Data Login Table

Login_Table		
Field_Name	Data_Type	Type description
User_Name	Varchar(20)	The login username
Password	Varchar(20)	The login password of user

Table 3.2: Data Tables for URL Address

Field_Name	Data_Type	Width	Type description
URL_ID	Integer	5	For URL id
URL_Lemgth	Integer	5	The length of URL address
NumDots	Integer	5	Total number of dot(.) in the URL
NumDash	Integer	5	Number of slashes/dash in URL
NumHostname	Integer	5	Number of host names in URL

The login table holds login information for all users who works on system and interface as the first prompt users to see upon accessing the system. Login details (usernames and passwords) are used to authenticate users. The registration table holds details of new users of the distribution system.

Table 3.3: Phishing Based Feature Table

Field_Name	Data_Type	Width	Type description
Phishing_ID	Integer	5	For Phising id
URL_anchor	Integer	5	
Page_link	Integer	5	Page link for url
Page_rank	Integer	5	Page rank for url

Table 3.4: Domain Based Feature Table

Field_Name	Data_Type	Width	Type description
Subdomain_ID	Integer	5	For Phishing site identification number
Subdomian_Name	Varchar	20	For sub level domain name
Second_levelDomain	Varchar	20	Second level domain in url
TopLevel_Domain	Varchar	20	Top level domain in url

The domain based feature table holds information about URL such as id, subdomain name, second level domain, and top level domain etc.

Results and Discussion

Figure 4.1: Splash Screen

Figure 4.1 depicts the program splash screen, the first phishing site detection software interface with a progressive bar which displays the percentage that runs from 1 to 100%. The steps vary from 1% to 100%, and the user will be prompted to wait until the user log-in screen appears after it reaches 100%. This is the splash screen that appears when a program is initially launched to notify the user that it has been loaded. The loading progresses as shown in the progressive bar.

Figure 4.2: Log-in Menu

Figure 4.2 depicts the user log-in menu for users to supply user name and password; if they match, access will be granted; otherwise, access to the program main menu is denied. If the user enters the wrong user name or password, the application logs off user; but if password matches grants user an authorized access.

Figure 4.3: Program Main Menu

Figure 4.3 shows the program main menu, which has the register menu, report and exit icon. The phishing site registration and prediction icons are found in the pull-down menu of registration panel. The registration pull-down menu simply includes URL site registration and detection while the report pull-down menu includes URL registration, detection and URL statistics.

Figure 4.4: Phishing URL Address Detection Form

The URL address registration form acquired from the registration module is shown in Figure 4.4 the registration form includes fields URLID, URL address, number of dots, number of dash, atsymbol, URL length, number of underscores, ampersand, hash, percentage symbols, www, number of digits, letters, target and etc. The user is instructed to click analysis and detect icons to search for the most prevalent symbols used by attackers in URL addresses for phishing.

Figure 4.5: URL Address Registration Report

Figure 4.5 above shows URL address registration report with the attributes: URLID, URL address, number of dots, number of dash, atsymbol, URL length, number of underscores, ampersand, hash, percentage symbols, www, number of digits, letters, target and etc as displayed using VB.NET

report viewer control tool. The user has been granted some administrative rights like converting of reports to PDF format, excel or other database supported formats, with an interactive report viewer tools to zoom in/out.

Figure 4.6: Statistic Update Graph

Figure 4.6 above, shows the Statistics update graph with attributes frequency by target class. It shows the updated record for all phishing or trusted URLs as detected by the system and this helps, to keep a track record of how many phishing or trusted URLs the system has analyzed. From the record above, the system has successfully detected 10 trusted and 8 phishing URLs and this is always updated immediately detection is carried out.

5.0 Conclusion

The user interaction system for phishing URL detection and voice notification is a VB.Net application that was coded to detect phishing or trusted URLs. This is done by inputting the desired URL address and then system checks with the parameters of the URL which are URLID, URL address, number of dots, number of dash, atsymbol, URL length, number of underscores, ampersand, hash, percentage symbols, www, number of digits, letters, target as coded to confirm and based on the checks done; the system detects the URL as either phishing or trusted and gives a target result accompanied by a voice notification to the user which is done for prompt notification. This system is reliable and very efficient as tested and shown, and can be used by individuals and cooperate entities for detection and notification of malicious URLs. It can also be embedded in an anti-virus as an added application.

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URLS	CLASS
diaryofagameaddict.com	Phishing
slightlyofficer.net	Trusted
yahoo.com	Trusted
diaryofagameaddict.com	Phishing
divineenterprises.net	Trusted
slightlyofficer.net	Trusted
Kalantzis	Phishing
yahoo.com	Trusted
espdesign.com.au	Phishing
iamagameadict.com	Phishing
rupor.info	Phishing
svision-online.de/mgfi/administrator/components/com_babackup/classes/fx29id1.txt	Phishing
officeon.ch.ma/office.js?google_ad_format=728x90_as	Phishing
sn-gzzx.com	Phishing
sunlux.net/company/about.html	Phishing
outporn.com	Phishing
timothycopus.aimoo.com	Phishing
xindalawyer.com	Phishing
freeseicals.spb.ru/key/68703.htm	Phishing
deletespyware-adware.com	Phishing
orbowlada.strefa.pl/text396.htm	Phishing
ruiyangcn.com	Phishing
zkic.com	Phishing
adserving.favorit-network.com/eas?camp=19320;cre=mu&grpId=1738&tag_id=618&nums=FGApbjFAAA	Phishing
cracks.vg/d1.php	Phishing
juicypussyclips.com	Phishing
nuptialimages.com	Phishing
andysgame.com	Phishing
bezproudoff.cz	Phishing
ceskarepublika.net	Phishing
hotspot.cz	Phishing
gmcjjh.org/DHL	Phishing
nerez-schodiste-zabradli.com	Phishing
nordiccountry.cz	Phishing
nowina.info	Phishing

obada-konstruksiwa.org	Phishing
otylkaaotesanek.cz	Phishing
pb-webdesign.net	Phishing
pension-helene.cz	Phishing
podzemi.myotis.info	Phishing

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